

A mathematical model of intrusion detection system based on PCA

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Abstract: This paper shows a mathematical formulation of traditional principal component analysis (PCA) in a new way and also describes that we can also detect the intrusion using a time-bandwidth product. Next, we tried to prove that introduction of intrusion is always lognormal distributed while the whole packet information is Gaussian statistics. After that we introduce a channel model of lognormal and gaussian statistics using existing literature studies. This work will benefit not only the intrusion detection system (IDS) of cyber security but also search for extraterrestrial studies.

Keywords: *IDS, SETI, PCA, lognormal, IDS communication model*

1. Introduction

In cyber security and search for extraterrestrial intelligence studies, the intrusion detection largely uses PCA[1,2,5]. PCA is an eigenvector analysis which depicts the pattern that lies in the signal. Karhunen-Loeve transform (KLT) is also a synonym of PCA which is used in the signal processing domain. Here we define slight changes of mathematical formulation of the SETI, Italian mathematician Dr. Maccone's "Final Variance theorem" for PCA analysis [1] which is thought of as an equality in [5]. In many studies curve fitting in statistics of intrusion data but why it is so, is never given in literature according to author's knowledge. Instead we

provide literature studies to prove our topics. The theme of the paper is awareness of specific literatures which were not used by either cyber security or SETI studies. We also did a novel mathematical formulation of KLT using prolate spheroid wave function (PSWF) study. The PSWF is the basis vector of KLT or PCA [7]. The PSWF is first introduced by time-frequency duality in Strum-Luovile problem. Later Slepian, Pollack introduced it in literature with new zeal. So, it is also called the Slepian series. PSWF is used in several studies to enhance the power spectral densities of low signal to noise (SNR) signals i.e., GPS, EEG/MEG, Thompson's multitaper method and so on [3, 4, 8]. A real time application of KLT can be found in [2]. The compressive sensing based on PSWF is described in [3] for GPS signals. The PSWF has only two parameters i.e, time bandwidth product (TBP) and sequence length which is also related to the TBP. In MATLAB or other programming language the PSWF is known as discrete prolate spheroid sequence (DPSS). The PSWF can be approximated using Legendre, Bessel, Hermite etc polynomials.

Next we present the fact of lognormal statistics

which is seen by many scientists while curve fitting the intrusion packet data analysis [9]. Here we give proof that the incoming establishment cost of packet data has to cross the "SNR wall" and the limited initial packet data is log-normal distributed.

At last, we model the Gaussian distribution to lognormal distribution by modelling an approach from existing literature of electronics communication. The Caterpillar Singular Spectrum Analysis (SSA) [5] is also extended to Bordered-Autocorrelation-Method (BAM) KLT [1]. The distribution change one can follow the stochastic distance like Kullback Leiber, Wasserstein, Helinger and Reny beta divergences.

In section II we describe the work on PCA or KLT, and Caterpillar SSA approach change for continuous and real time monitoring of the network. In the line of continuation of KLT, the lognormal distribution and "SNR wall" and its detection is described in section III. In section IV we discuss mathematical models and lastly in section V we conclude this article.

2. Demystifying KLT

Let $x(t)$ is an arbitrary signal. Its KLT expression $X(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Z_n \phi_n(t) \dots (1)$

Let $E\{x(t)\} = 0$ where $E\{\}$ stands for average operator $E\{Z_n\} = 0$

$$\sigma_{2n}^2 = E\{Z_n\} - E\{Z_n^2\} = E\{Z_n^2\}$$

Using Euler Formula like Fourier Transform we can write

$$Z_n = \int_0^t x(t) \phi_n(t) dt \dots (2)$$

The uncorrelated terms comes from the autocorrelation of a random signal of time $x(t)$ is defined at

$$R_{xx}(t_1, t_2) = E\{x(t_1)x(t_2)\}$$

If $E\{x(t)\}$ vanishes identically in $0 \leq t \leq T$. The autocorrelation reduces to the variance of $x(t)$ when two instants are the same.

$$\sigma_{x(t)}^2 = E\{x^2(t)\} = R_x(t, t)$$

Now

$$E\{x(t_1)x(t_2)\} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_m \phi_m(t_1) \phi_m(t_2) \dots (3)$$

As Z_n can be obtained by projecting $x(t)$ over the corresponding eigen vector in Hilbert space, which is the infinite dimensional Euclidean space spanned by the eigenvector $\phi_n(t)$ that the square of $\phi_n(t)$ is integrable over the final time span $0 \leq t \leq T$ so,

ϕ_n are w-bandlimited, orthogonal on R^m

$$\int_{R^m} \phi_m(t_1)\phi_n(t_2)' d\sigma(t) = \sigma_{m,n}$$

i.e. Kromeeckor delta and complete in the w-bandlimited signals

$$A_w = \{f \in L^2(R^m, R^{m+1}) \mid \text{supremum } F(f) \subseteq w \subseteq R^m\}$$

$$\text{And } \int_T |f(t)|^2 \delta\sigma(t) > 0$$

Because a positive real eigenvalues $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \lambda_3 \dots \geq 0$. Each eigenvalue has finite multiplicity. The eigen function constitutes the m-dimensional PSWF associated with the set of w and T . They are orthogonal on T and constitute an orthogonal basis of $L^2(T, R^{m+1})$ because 0 is not an eigenvalue of such a positive operator. They are orthogonal on R^m which can be shown by orthogonality over finite region T . So, ϕ_n are orthogonal and complete in $L^2(T, R^{M+1,1})$

$$\int_T \phi_m(t)\phi_n(t) d\delta(t) = \lambda_n \delta_{m,n}$$

$$\|\phi_n\|^2 \text{ at } L^2(R^m, R^{m+1}) = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\|\phi_n\|^2 \text{ at } L^2(T, R^{m+1}) = \lambda_n$$

A small value of λ_n implies $\phi_n(t)$ has most of its energy outside the interval T .

Now from equation (1)

$$\int_0^T E\{x(t_1)x(t_2)\}\phi_n(t_1)\delta t_1 = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \lambda_m \phi_m(t_2) \int_0^T \phi_m(t_1)\phi_n(t_2)\delta(t_1)$$

$$= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \lambda_m \phi_m(t_2) \lambda_n \delta_{m,n} \dots \dots (4)$$

Using Maccone's "final variance theorem" the domain eigenvalue of autocorrelation matrix (Z_n) so, differentiate w.r.t instant time T and output is variance. From equation (3)

$$E\{X^2(t)\} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n \phi_n^2(t)$$

As the ϕ_n is normalized to 1, so that $\int_0^T \phi_n^2(t) = \lambda_n$ over timespan $0 \leq t \leq T$

$$\int_0^T E\{x^2(t)\} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^2$$

$$\int_0^T \sigma_x^2(t) \delta t = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^2 \dots (5)$$

so, the series of eigenvalue λ_n is coverage as the upper limit T so, λ_n , so λ_n is a function of

T

$$\lambda_n = \lambda_n(T)$$

$$\sigma_x^2(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\delta \lambda_n^2(T)}{\delta T} \approx \frac{\delta \lambda_1^2(T)}{\delta T} = \sigma_x(t) \approx T \text{ but } \sqrt{T} \text{ as final variance theorem} \dots$$

(6)

$$\mathbf{X}=(x_{ij})_{i,j=1}^{k,L} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & \dots & x_L \\ x_2 & x_3 & x_4 & \dots & x_{L+1} \\ x_3 & x_4 & x_5 & \dots & x_{L+2} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_k & x_{k+1} & x_{k+2} & \dots & x_k \end{bmatrix} \dots (7)$$

where $L < K$ is called Caterpillar length. The BAM-KLT defines that if we add new row and column at to the last row and column to the new packet data as it is function of $\lambda(T)$ to $\lambda(T + 1)$. When the variance changes to lognormal we can tell the intrusion.

The PSWF in compressive sensing used this [3, 4] are following

$$p(n) = \text{sinc}(2w(m - n)) \dots (8)$$

3. Lognormal distribution for intrusion

Neyman-Pearson energy detector or radiometric detector is used for spectrum sensors. Traditional; upper bound of Pdf of false alarm and lower bound of Pdf of detection.

$$r_x = |n_t | H_0 \quad x_t \in N(0, \sigma^2)$$

$$r_x = |x_t + n_t | H_1$$

Gaussian Decision making converts binary

$$d_t = \pi(r_t) \quad \delta_t \in 0,1$$

π mapping decision function

Q is Marcum function and the probability described in [10] are

$$P_{false} = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{M}{2}} \frac{E(x(t)^2)/M}{\sigma_n^2} - 1\right)$$

$$P_{d,t} = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{M}{2}} \frac{E(x(t)^2)/M}{\sigma_n^2 + \sigma_{x,t}^2} - 1\right) \dots (9)$$

$$E[\sigma_n^2] = \sigma_n^2$$

$$\text{Variance} = u\sigma_n^4$$

$$u \text{ is uncertainty } u = 10^{\frac{u_{dB}}{10}} - 1$$

$$\sigma_n^2 = \log N(\mu_u, V_u)$$

$$V_u = \log(1+U)$$

$$\mu_u = 2 \log(\sigma_n) - \frac{V_u}{2}$$

$$V_T = 2 \log \left(1 + \frac{2}{M} \right)$$

$$\mu_u = 2 \log(\sigma) - \frac{V_T}{2}$$

$$W = \log \left(\frac{T_t}{M \sigma_n^2} \right)$$

$$\gamma^{SNR wall} = \exp(\Delta \sqrt{\text{Variance}(W)}) - 1$$

whereas V is variance and M is degree of freedom From (6)

$$\sigma_x^2 \propto T$$

For turbulence (σ_T^2) aperture is comparable to correlation length [12]

$$\sigma_x \propto \sqrt{TW} \propto \sigma_h / \sigma_v$$

w is wavelength irradiance fluctuation averaged and changed to lognormal .

The correlation time

$$\sigma_T^2 = \sigma_G^2 \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} h_k^2$$

$$x_i = \sum_{x=0}^{m-1} h_k Z_{(i-k)}$$

Output is lognormal $aT_i = \exp(x_i - \sigma_i^2/2)$

.The block diagram is shown in fig 1. The Lowpass filter may be Krohn Height filter.

Fig. 1 Block diagram of intrusion packet data from Gaussian to lognormal

4. Observation

Fig 2 It represent the filtered signal

5. Discussion

We have tried to modify the “Final variance theorem” by introducing PSWF. And also Dr. Maccone depicts in his article that the estimated signal’s frequency is twice of the original frequency. As we have 2 term which explains that the frequency must be twice. Next, we explained the BAM-KLT. Here the new packet introduction is adding a new row and column of Caterpillar SSA. The easiest way to solution is the function of $2(T)$. Hence the function variance change also signifies the network capacity and lognormal distributed packet information. After that we introduce the lognormal variable which is caused by the SNR wall. In every electronics equipment, a higher or an amount of current is required to change its state from static to dynamic. So this also applies for signal introduction. Lastly, we show the block diagram in fig 1, which is the suitable modelling of network traffic data approach. Hence we can say that this paper benefits the cyber security and SETI domains.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we did not show on the network traffic dataset but tells the way with existing literatures. Here the KLT derivation is novel but in some way biased by existing literature of PSWF. We connected the dots. In future work we try the simulation or real data set signal processing. Here we connect two esteemed domains under the same umbrella.

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